

Modification of photocatalytic activity of antimony(III) sulphide in presence of sodium bicarbonate/carbonate

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Manuscript received 10 March 2005, revised 8 June 2005, accepted 21 June 2005

A comparative study of photocatalytic bleaching of azure-B over Sb_2S_3 powder was carried out in the presence and absence of sodium bicarbonate/carbonate. The photocatalytic bleaching was observed to be more efficient in the presence of bicarbonate/carbonate ions. The effect of various parameters has been studied and a tentative mechanism for the photocatalytic bleaching has been proposed.

In an increasingly industrialized world, the problem of degradation of waste products is very serious from ecological point of view. Among these, the industries using dyes and pigments such as textiles, tannery, paper, pulp and printing industries are the biggest source of polluting the environment^{1,2}. The effluents of such industries are highly colored, complex and toxic. Several methods of treatment of these effluents have been undertaken from time to time, the most common of which are chemical precipitation and biological methods. However, these methods have many disadvantages like chemical handling, sludge disposal and long-term biodegradation³. One of the recent approaches, which is very effective and economic too is "photocatalytic treatment of waste water"⁴. It is an eco-friendly route of treating pollutants. It decolorises the colored effluents and thereby reduces pollution. Among the commonly used photocatalysts are : TiO_2 , ZnO , $SrTiO_3$ etc. The use of sulphides for this purpose is still meagre. Some of the earlier studies were focused on CdS , ZnS , etc⁵. It has been found that the photocatalytic activity of semiconductors may be enhanced by doping them with 3d-transition metal ions⁶; heat treatment with alkali metal halides⁷ and addition of bicarbonate or carbonate⁸ ions etc. The present work has been undertaken to investigate the photocatalytic bleaching of azure-B over antimony(III) sulphide powder, a sulphide photocatalyst in presence of bicarbonate/carbonate ions.

Results and discussion

A plot of $(1 + \log [\text{absorbance}])$ vs time was found to be linear indicating that the photocatalytic bleaching of azure-B follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate con-

stant (k) for the reaction was determined using the expression, $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$.

A comparative study of the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue in the presence and absence of sodium bicarbonate/sodium carbonate was carried out. It was observed that photobleaching was more efficient in the presence of bicarbonate/carbonate ions, as reflected by the values of the rate constants [with and without $NaHCO_3$, $k = 2.84 \times 10^{-4}$ and $9.59 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$; with and without Na_2CO_3 , $k = 2.84 \times 10^{-4}$ and $9.26 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively].

Effect of $NaHCO_3$ and Na_2CO_3 concentration : The effect of concentration of $NaHCO_3$ and Na_2CO_3 was studied by carrying out experiments at different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate/sodium carbonate (Table 1). It was observed that the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of azure-B increases on increasing the concentrations of $NaHCO_3/Na_2CO_3$ to a certain limit beyond which it decreases on increasing the concentration of $NaHCO_3/Na_2CO_3$ further. This may be due to the reaction of bicarbonate/carbonate species with holes in semiconductor leading to charge separation, which restricts the recombination of electron with holes. An increase in concentration of HCO_3^-/CO_3^{2-} ions will increase the number of hole traps; as a consequence of which, the reaction rate increases. However, an increase in concentration of HCO_3^-/CO_3^{2-} ions beyond a limit may lead to the formation of their multilayer instead of a monolayer over semiconductor surface. The formation of multilayer will not permit the HCO_3^-/CO_3^{2-} ions on the surface to act as a hole trap. Consequently, a decrease in the rate of reaction has been observed.

Table 1. Effect of sodium carbonate or bicarbonate concentration

For Na ₂ CO ₃ :		For NaHCO ₃ :	
pH=9.0		pH=8.0	
[Azure-B] = 2.50 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Azure-B] = 2.50 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
Light intensity = 30.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	
Antimony trisulphide = 0.14 g		Antimony trisulphide = 0.12 g	
[Na ₂ CO ₃] or [NaHCO ₃] ×		<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	
	For Na ₂ CO ₃	For NaHCO ₃	
10 ³ M			
1.00	15.98	18.87	
1.50	17.04	20.06	
2.00	18.26	21.31	
2.50	21.30	28.41	
3.00	17.75	26.64	
3.50	15.98	25.08	
4.00	14.20	23.22	

Effect of pH : The rate of reaction increases with increase in pH to an optimum value beyond which the rate decreases on increasing the pH value of the medium (Table 2). This is because the HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻ ions are more stable in alkaline solution. The reaction rate increases on increasing pH and reaches an optimum value for bicarbonate (pH = 8.0) and carbonate (pH = 9.0). On increasing the pH above this limit, the concentration of OH⁻ ions will also increase, thus a competition for adsorption is created between OH⁻ ions and HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻ ions, where OH⁻ ions get as edge due to their smaller size and

Table 2. Effect of pH

For Na ₂ CO ₃ :		For NaHCO ₃ :	
[Azure-B] = 2.50 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Azure-B] = 2.50 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	
Light intensity = 30.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	
Antimony trisulphide = 0.14 g		Antimony trisulphide = 0.12 g	
[Na ₂ CO ₃] = 2.50 × 10 ⁻³ M		<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	
pH	For Na ₂ CO ₃	For NaHCO ₃	
5.0	10.64	18.93	
5.5	11.77	20.93	
6.0	12.90	22.71	
6.5	13.31	24.35	
7.0	14.19	25.25	
7.5	15.78	26.84	
8.0	18.52	28.41	
8.5	19.87	26.23	
9.0	21.30	25.83	
9.5	19.35	25.32	
10.0	16.57	24.80	

high charge density. Hence in the presence of OH⁻ ions, HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻ ions will not be able to act as hole trap as effectively as earlier and a corresponding decrease in the rate of reaction was observed.

Effect of azure-B concentration : The rate of photocatalytic bleaching increases with increase in concentration of azure-B upto a certain limit beyond which, it decreases (Table 3). This may be attributed to the fact that with the increase in concentration of dye, more dye molecules are available for excitation and consecutive energy transfer resulting in an increase in the rate of reaction. However, with the increase in dye concentration beyond a limit (azure-B = 2.5 × 10⁵ M) the dye starts acting like internal filter for the incident light. It will not permit the desired light intensity to reach and excite large number of semiconductor particles resulting in a decrease in rate of reaction.

Table 3. Effect of azure-B concentration

For Na ₂ CO ₃ :		For NaHCO ₃ :	
pH=9.0		pH=8.0	
Light intensity = 30.0 mW cm ⁻²		Light intensity = 60.0 mW cm ⁻²	
Antimony trisulphide = 0.14 g		Antimony trisulphide = 0.12 g	
[Na ₂ CO ₃] = 2.50 × 10 ⁻³ M		<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	
[Azure-B] × 10 ⁵ M	For Na ₂ CO ₃	For NaHCO ₃	
1.0	18.92	18.93	
1.5	19.88	22.97	
2.0	20.62	27.05	
2.5	21.30	28.41	
3.0	19.02	27.85	
3.5	17.86	27.61	
4.0	14.94	27.14	

Effect of amount of semiconductor : The rate of reaction increases with an increase in the amount of Sb₂S₃ but after a certain value, it becomes virtually constant (Table 4). This may be due to the fact that as the amount of semiconductor was increased, the exposed surface area also increases resulting into an increase in the reaction rate. But after a certain limit, there is no increase in the exposed surface area of the photocatalyst but simply an increase in the thickness of the layer at the bottom of the vessel. Thus, the rate of reaction becomes almost constant.

Effect of light intensity : The rate of photocatalytic bleaching of azure-B was found to increase on increasing the light intensity, but after a certain limit, the rate de-

Table 4. Effect of amount of semiconductor

Amount of semiconductor (g)	$k \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	
	For Na ₂ CO ₃	For NaHCO ₃
0.04	13.38	15.17
0.06	15.54	18.92
0.08	18.59	22.72
0.10	20.08	25.56
0.12	21.14	28.41
0.14	21.30	28.40
0.16	21.28	28.44
0.18	21.30	28.42
0.20	21.32	28.41

creases on increasing the intensity of light (Table 5). An increase in the intensity of light will increase the number of photons striking the semiconductor particles per unit area per unit time. As a result, more electron-hole pairs are generated, which results in an overall increase in the rate of reaction. However, at higher light intensities, some thermal side reactions may also start and hence, the rate of photocatalytic bleaching decreases on increasing the intensity of light further.

Table 5. Effect of light intensity

Light intensity (mW cm ⁻²)	$k \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	
	For Na ₂ CO ₃	For NaHCO ₃
20.0	19.66	22.07
30.0	21.30	24.85
40.0	20.44	27.33
50.0	19.56	28.41
60.0	18.73	26.44
70.0	17.88	24.93
80.0	17.02	21.78

Mechanism :

On the basis of the experimental observations and corroborating existing literature, a tentative mechanism

has been proposed for the photocatalytic bleaching of azure-B (AB) over antimony trisulphide (SC) powder in the presence of sodium bicarbonate or sodium carbonate.

(leuco form)

Dye absorbs a photon and converted into its first singlet excited state (¹AB₁) which will change into its triplet excited state (³AB₁) via inter-system crossing (ISC). The hole is trapped by CO₃²⁻ ions to give carbonate anion radical CO₃^{•-}. The bicarbonate also generate these radical anions by combining with hole to given HCO₃[•] radical and its decomposition into H⁺ and CO₃^{•-}. Such two carbonate anion radicals combine to give peroxycarbonate species (C₂O₆²⁻), which is easily decomposed by reacting with holes into O₂ and CO₂. These bicarbonate or carbonate species on semiconductor surface play an important role in the desorption of oxygen via carbonate anion radical. Now, the electrons present in the conduction band of the semiconductor will reduce the triplet excited state of dye into its leuco form, which will finally degrade into products.

Experimental

Stock solutions of azure-B (1.0 × 10⁻³ M), sodium bicarbonate (0.02 M) or sodium carbonate (0.02 M) were prepared in double-distilled water. In the first set, 0.9 mL of azure-B solution, 0.8 mL of sodium bicarbonate solution and 38.3 mL water were mixed. The pH of reaction mixture was adjusted to 8.0 and then 0.12 g of antimony trisulphide was added to it. In another experiment 0.8 mL of 1.0 × 10⁻³ M azure-B solution, 0.9 mL of 0.02 M sodium carbonate solution and 38.3 mL of water were mixed. The pH of reaction mixture was adjusted to 9.0 and then 0.14 g of antimony trisulphide (Reidel) was

added to it.

These reaction mixtures were exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp. A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiations. The progress of the reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 650 \text{ nm}$.

Acknowledgement

One of us (R.A.) is thankful to U.G.C. for providing a Project Fellowship.

References

1. G. McKay and S. J. Allen, *Canad. J. Chem. Engg.*, 1980, **58**, 521.
2. G. McKay S. J. Alles, I. F. McConvey and M. S. Otterbum, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1981, **80**, 323.
3. C. Y. Hsiao, C. L. Lee and D. F. Ollis, *J. Catal.*, 1983, **82**, 418.
4. M. Wolkenstein, *Adv. Catal.*, 1973, **23**, 157; G. Somorjai, *New J. Photochem.*, 1987, **11**, 197; M. Gratzel (ed.), "Energy Resources through Photochemistry and Catalysis", Academic Press, New York, 1983; Suresh C. Ameta, Bhawana Singhal, Sarita Jain and Mukesh Parakh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 1001; Suresh C. Ameta, Pinki B. Punjabi, Pratibha Rao and Bhawana Singhal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 157.
5. Kobayakawa, T. Miura, A. Suzuki, Y. Sato and A. Fujishima, *Solar Energy Mater., Solar Cells*, 1993, **30**, 201; Neeru Chhabra, Rajat Ameta, Jitendra Vardia and Suresh C. Ameta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 687; B. R. Eggine, P. K. J. Robertson, J. H. Stewart and E. Woods, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, 349.
6. K. Wada, K. Yoshida, Y. Watanabe and T. Suzuki, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 726; A. Ashok Kumar and P. Maruthamuthu, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 1989, **24**, 2135.
7. F. Nakahara and A. Nagae, *Zairyo*, 1970, **19**, 528; K. Kobayakawa, T. Miura, A. Suzuki, Y. Sato and A. Fujishima, *Solar Energy Mater., Solar Cells*, 1993, **30**, 201.
8. K. Sayana and H. Arakawa, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1996, **94**, 67.